

UNDERSTANDING SYCOSIS THROUGH WARTS: A CLINICAL INSIGHT INTO THUJA OCCIDENTALIS

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND

Warts are generally non-cancerous rough bumps or outgrowths on the skin of the body, mostly on hand and feet, and caused by several strains of human papilloma virus, the virus produce an excess amount of keratin, a hard protein, over the top skin layer resulting in formation of rough, hard texture.¹ They are the benign proliferative lesions that occur at any ages in human lives.²

Warts are the growth of skin resulting from human papillomavirus infection. These may be single, multiple, smooth, or cauliflower-like.³

Currently, more than 150 types of HPV have been identified. Certain HPV types tend to infest skin at particular anatomical sites; however, warts of any HPV type may occur at any site.⁴ Warts are classified under one sided diseases as external local maladies, they often have individualistic and immunological basis as also familial tendencies.⁵

INTRODUCTION

Master Hahnemann found in thuja the antidote to the miasm of the condition which he termed sycosis, meaning thereby the constitutional disease resulting from constitutional gonorrhoea, and having as its characteristic manifestation of like excrescences, sometimes dry in the form of warts, more frequently soft, spongy, emitting a foetid fluid with a sweetish odour something like herring brine, bleeding readily and having the coxcomb or cauliflower like appearance.⁶

The main action of thuja is on the skin and genito-urinary organs, producing conditions that correspond with Hahnemann's sycotic dyscrasia, whose chief manifestation is the formation of wart-like excrescences upon mucus and cutaneous surfaces, fig-warts and condylomata. Has a specific antibacterial action, as in gonorrhoea and vaccination.¹²

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Literature review was done from search databases like google scholar, research gate, reference articles and various homoeopathic websites, focusing on the phytochemical properties, pharmacological activity and clinical application of thuja occidentalis, particularly in the treatment of cutaneous warts.

RESULTS:

Summary of the case: A male patient of age 55 years, came to the clinic with the complaints of old warts which are cauliflower-like and dark in colour on the left side of the nose, on homoeopathic treatment after considering case analysis and

further repertorial analysis, the chosen similimum Thuja 200C is proven to be effective in curing the condition.

CONCLUSION: Warts are benign skin growths caused by the human papilloma virus (HPV) that occur in the mucosa and skin. They resolve spontaneously but treatment is taken to avoid spreading. The case illustrated in this article highlights the efficacy of Thuja in treating warts due to its anti-viral, antiproliferative, proapoptotic, and antiangiogenic properties.

KEY WORDS – Thuja occidentalis, condylomata, warts, sycosis, phytoconstituents of thuja, thujone and its action.

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INTRODUCTION

TAXONOMICAL CLASSIFICATION

Domain: Eukaryota

Kingdom: Plantae

Subkingdom: Viridaeplantae

Phylum: Pinophyta

Subphylum: Euphyllophytina

Infraphylum: Radiatopses

Class: Pinopsida

Order: Pinales

Family: Cupressaceae

Tribe: Spiraeae

Genus: Thuja

Specific epithet: Occidentalis

Botanical name: *Thuja occidentalis*.⁷

THUJA OCCIDENTALIS

Thuja species are generally used as antiviral, antibacterial, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, anti-HIV, anti-fungal etc. Antiviral and immunopharmacological action of thuja, as stimulatory effects on cytokine and antibody production and also active macrophages cells, have been tested in various in vivo and invitro study.⁷ Phytochemical analysis of thuja occidentalis revealed the presence of alkaloids, glycosides, phenols, flavonoids.⁸

Thuja species have different chemical substances like thujone, Isothujone, fenchone, sabinens and alpha- pinen.⁷ Thuja occidentalis is used to treat a variety of ailments with its oil and leaves, researchers have discovered that thujone has antiproliferative, proapoptotic, and antiangiogenic

properties in vitro that may lower cell viability, additionally stopping the spread of melanoma in living things. The effectiveness of *T. occidentalis* extracts as antiviral agents against the HSV-2 and H1N1 viruses was studied.⁹

Thuja occidentalis is commonly used homoeopathic remedy for treating cutaneous warts. It is particularly indicated for warts that are large, jagged, or cauliflower-like in appearance. It is also used for warts that bleed easily.¹⁰

SYCOSIS:

Hahnemann has published the first homoeopathic *Materia Medica* of *Thuja occidentalis* in 1834. He made *Thuja occidentalis* the leader in homoeopathic medicines for sycosis, which he described as a chronic miasma of venereal origin, causing growths of the skin and mucous membranes.¹¹

This fig-wart, which in later times, especially during the French war, in the years 1809-1814, was so widely spread, but which has since showed itself more and more rarely, was treated, almost always, in an inefficient and injurious manner, internally with mercury, because it was considered homogenous with the venereal chancre-disease; but the excrescences on the genitals were treated by allopathic physicians always in the most violent external way by cauterizing, burning and cutting or by ligatures. These excrescences usually first manifest themselves on genitals, and usually but not always, attend with a sort of gonorrhoea from the urethra, several days or several weeks, even many weeks after infection through coition; more rarely they appear dry and like warts, more frequently soft, spongy, emitting a fetid fluid, bleeding easily, and in the form of cox comb or cauliflower (*brassica botrytis*). For the fig-wart miasm, which rules in the whole organism, has been in no way diminished, either by the external destruction of the above-mentioned excrescences, or by the mercury which has been used internally, and which is in no way appropriate to sycosis. The gonorrhoea dependent on the fig-wart miasma, as well as the above-mentioned excrescences are cured most truly most thoroughly the internal use of *Thuja*.¹³

THUJA OCCIDENTALIS – HOMOEOPATHIC REMEDY

Common name: Tree of life, white cedar.

Preparation: The mother tincture is prepared from the fresh leaves, collected when the plant is just flowering and dilutions are made, as directed under class II. D.P. of the tincture: 1/2.¹⁴

Physiological action: It acts on the skin and genito-urinary organs, producing a condition that corresponds to sycosis. *Thuja* has the singular property of softening hard tissue. It has the ability to remove warts, it softens them and causes their absorption.¹⁴

Constitution: Patient has a waxy shiny face and it looks as if it had been smeared over with grease and is often transparent. He is sickly looking person and looks as if entering up on some cachexia. *Thuja* is the only efficacious remedy for fig-warts and gonorrhoea. They are fleshy having undue and unwanted growths, tumours, cyst etc. Having dark hair and dark complexion, unhealthy oily skin, dirty brownish with white spots.¹⁵ *Thuja* patients are hard people. The hardness in their emotional expression manifest even on physical level-as hard tumours. Just so, the ugliness in their soul manifests as ugliness in the tumours.¹⁶

Mind: thuja patients have the feeling of fragility which in physical sphere, express as the patient feels that any article of food or drink is surely bound to cause him problems, and that his system cannot take things such as drugs, allergens, emotional stress or even a draught of air. He tries to avoid all these factors and attempts to keep himself covered from exposure to the same. These avoidances only reinforce the fear, and making the thuja one of the main remedies for neurosis, with several obsessive-compulsive traits, fixed ideas, and behaviour pattern.

Thuja women can be very afraid of pregnancy, and often have the sensation of being pregnant. These women can be jealous, and may have fixed ideas that the husband is faithless. Thuja people often exhibit a preference of green colour.¹⁷

Fixed ideas, as if strange person were at his side, as if soul and body were separated, as if something alive in abdomen without pain, but remaining stationary in eyes. Mental depression after childbirth. Walks in a circle. Thinks his blood is dirty or poisoned. Aversion to life.¹⁸

Begin to twitch at approach of strangers, sudden impulse to kill herself.¹⁹

He or she is very slow to trust others, and you sense that there is more than the usual secretiveness. He learns not to display his real character any more, even though the tendencies remain inside and continue to cry out for expression. He finds way to cheat. He becomes very proper. It is as if he has found out that being freely expressive of his instincts does not pay in society, so he becomes very controlled. Thuja patients are always reserved. They do not allow any form of deep communication.¹⁶

Face: skin greasy, pale, waxy, shiny, dark under eyes, tumours on cheeks, warts.¹⁸

Scalp: white dandruff. Hair falls off or grows slowly and then splits. Hairs becomes dry, hard and lusterless and fall out. Biting and corrosive gnawing in the right side of the hairy scalp, in the evening. Corrosive itching, continuous stich in the hairy scalp, obliging him to scratch. Sensation in the hairs of the right side of the head as if a cluster of hairs were being electrified; a sort of creeping in the hairs and a tendency to stand on end, with a slight shuddering of the skin under the hairs.²⁰

Vaccinosis: animal poisoning: thuja is pre-eminently a strong medicine when you have a trace of animal poisoning in the history, as a snake bite, small-pox, and vaccination. Diarrhea or any skin disease following vaccination, particularly in children.²¹

Rectum: gurling in bowels, the painless watery green stools. Chronic diarrhoea, worse after breakfast. Anus fissured, painful to touch. Anal warts. Moisture oozing from anus. Haemorrhoids swollen, pain worse sitting with stiching, burning pains in the anus.¹⁸

Fissure: fissures about the anus, on perineum, on scrotum, even on glans penis. These fissures are painful to touch. Fissured anus may be surrounded with warts. All thuja fissures are deep and contain pus. Fistula in anus.²¹

Urinary organs: frequent micturition, almost every hour, but no pain. The stream is interrupted five to six times, before urine is entirely voided. Sensation after micturition as if some drops were running out of the urethra, for a quarter of an hour. Burning in urethra, between the act of

micturition. Frequent urging to urinate, and frequent micturition, without pain. The urine looks like watery while coming out; after long standing.²⁰

Male sexual organs: it is of service on sub-acute and chronic gonorrhoea. The glans penis may be red and smooth, or there are fig warts and condylomata over the sexual organs, that exude a glutinous, foul-smelling matter.²²

Erection for several hours, early in the morning, when half asleep. Sweat on one-half of the scrotum.²⁰

Female sexual organs: the walls of the vagina, external genitals may be covered with the warty excrescences which are attended with great burning and smarting pains. The parts are extremely sensitive to touch. It is also of service in idiopathic condylomata of the moist form, and bleeding fungous growths and epithelioma and cauliflower excrescences, polypi of the uterus and vagina which bleed easily and emit a foul odour. They are attended with profuse mucus leucorrhoea which is extremely acrid and excoriates the uterus, vulva, and perineum.

It is useful when the ovaries congested, especially the left. There is a burning pain, which is worse during menstruation, while walking and riding. The menses are delayed and scanty. There is a desire to masturbate, even during sleep.²²

Miscarriage at third month.

Sleep: sleepless when lying on left. lascivious dreams without emission of semen with painful erections on waking.¹⁸

Skin-Growth: Wart-like excrescences on mucous and cutaneous surfaces. They appear here and there, especially on hands and genitals. Warts with little necks. Warts hard, cleft and seedy. They often split easily.²¹

CASE REPORT

Presenting complaint: A 55year old male, approached to the clinic with the complaints of large wart on the left side of his nose, and small wart on the root of the nose, which had gradually increasing in size over past 14 years

H/O presenting complaints: patient gradually developed warts on left side of nose and at the root of the nose, these were increasing in size and number. There are no associated symptoms like bleeding or pain. Previously had warts on eyes, nose, lips, brows. O/E, Warts were found to be pedunculated (having a stalk), cauliflower like and dark in colour.

Treatment history: The patient previously consulted allopathic doctors, who advised surgical removal of the wart, but he was unwilling to undergo surgery.

Past history: Chicken pox at the age of 4 years.

Physical generals:

Generals- good,

Thermals- Chilly patient

Mental generals: He has particular beliefs in religious matters and domestic affairs (fixed ideas).

Life space investigation: Patient hails from a middle-class family. Relationship with family is good. He studied up to inter and now working as a courier delivery person.

Totality of symptoms:

1. He has particular beliefs in religious matters and domestic affairs
2. Old warts on face on the left side of nose
3. Face is greasy and shiny
4. Oily face
5. Cauliflower like growths on the left side of nose

Repertorial result:

Follow up:

S.no	DATE	COMPLAINT	TREATMENT
1	27/01/25	Large wart on the left side of his nose, and small wart on the root of the nose	1.Thuja 200C 3 doses for 3 days 2. Phytum 6/6 1 month
2	23/02/25	Warts disappeared	Sac Lac 1 month
3	23/03/25	Generalised Condition- fair No further reoccurrence of Warts	Sac lac 1 month

BEFORE

AFTER

CONCLUSION: A case report of warts successfully managed with homeopathic medicine *thuja 200C* highlights the effectiveness and potentiality of homeopathy in addressing chronic, sycotic warts. The case is treated by individualising in both physical and mental plane of the person with the principle of “like cures like”.

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